

$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{a,2}^{\text{H}^+}$ show the same selectivity order i.e., $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{SCN}^- > \text{I}^- > \text{NO}_3^-$.

TABLE 2—STANDARD FREE ENERGY CHANGE OF AN ION EXCHANGE REACTION

Anion	$\Delta G_{a,2}^{\text{H}^+}$ k cal mole ⁻¹
ClO_4^-	-2.45
SCN^-	-1.59
I^-	-1.312
NO_3^-	-0.77

One can thus say that Diamond's water structure enforced ion pairing and Reichenberg's hydration free energy concepts are complementary to each other.

Most of the observed phenomena can be explained by the effects of the organic solvent on the structure of water and by the preferential ion-solvation effects. On adding formamide, the external solution becomes a poorer and poorer solvating medium because of the continuous breaking up of the water structure. Though formamide is protic it will not form long chain hydrogen bonding with increased formamide content and it strongly competes with water for ion-solvent interactions and both these effects may result in the reduction of selectivity of the preferred ion. The values in Table 1 show the reduction in $K_{a,2}^{\text{H}^+}$ with increase in formamide content of the ions studied except in the case of NO_3^- - Cl^- exchange where it exhibits an anomalous behaviour which may be due to its size, shape and also may be due to the weak electrolyte nature of nitric acid compared to others in the series. Bhat³ and Ramanathan *et al*^{1,2} have already reported increase in the selectivity of NO_3^- at 70% and above methanol content on weak and strong base exchangers.

The reduction in selectivity of preferred ion (bigger anion) with the increase in the formamide content can be explained as follows.

The partial replacement of water in an aqueous solution by dipolar, protic bigger dipoles of formamide has the following effect on the above system. Though protic, it too breaks the structure of water resulting in the increase of free energy of the system. But the larger anions of lower charge density get solvated by the formamide molecules by the ion dipole interactions making the broken water dipoles free to rejoin the structure of water. Thus, the free energy of the system will be reduced more and more with the increase in formamide concentration in the external solution medium. The external solution, therefore, will now prefer the bigger ion resulting in the decrease in the selectivity.

Another interesting point in these selectivity trends is the change in separation ratio of selectivity constants (corrected) with change in solvent composition. These selectivity constants gave less separation for I^- , SCN^- , and ClO_4^- in aqueous solutions (the ratio being 1 : 1.2 : 1.86) as compared to those obtained in mixed systems (1 : 1.93 : 3.7 in 40%)

Thus, mixed solvents can be of much greater utility for planning separation of these ions.

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Further Studies on Electrolytic Reduction of Nitrogen to Ammonia

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OF the various attempts¹ to reduce nitrogen to ammonia under extremely mild conditions, the one cursorily reported by Palit² involves the reduction of dissolved nitrogen near the cathode kept inside a narrow tube covered by a cellophane paper at the bottom during electrolysis of distilled water in a beaker under non-Faradaic conditions^{3,4}. This electrolytic reduction of nitrogen having technological importance and enzymatic significance is worth further study. The present note records a brief endeavour to find out the essential conditions and a plausible mechanism for the occurrence of the unusual phenomenon observed by Palit².

Experimental

To find out the necessary conditions for formation of ammonia by the electrolytic reduction of dissolved nitrogen, the electrolysis is at first carried out in a 1000 ml beaker containing 10^{-3} NH_4SO_4 with platinum foil electrodes (1 cm²) immersed in it, the cathode being kept in a cellophane covered glass tube (16 mm O.D.) containing distilled water (Fig. 1). Current is passed overnight from D. C.

mains. The liquid inside the tube is taken out and is found to give positive test with Nessler's reagent. The tube is repeatedly filled up with distilled water, electrolysis continued, and the solution from inside the tube withdrawn. Ammonia is detected in the solution every time. On titrating with acid solution, the strength of the solution after overnight electrolysis is found to be about $10^{-2}N$. At a slightly higher temperature (ca 40°) the formation of ammonia increases to some extent but no trace of ammonia could be detected on increasing the strength of the acid solution at the anode side i.e., outside the cathode tube.

Fig. 1

Secondly, a U-tube (32 mm O.D) is taken instead of the beaker and the electrolysis is carried out without keeping the cathode within the cellophane covered tube. Ammonia formation does not take place at all but as soon as the cathode is placed inside the cellophane covered glass tube (Fig. 2),

Fig. 2

measurable amount of ammonia is formed after electrolysis for 24 hr. So in essence, ammonia could be produced irrespective of the cell used

provided the cathode is kept separated from the rest of the electrolyte by a narrow glass tube the bottom end of which is covered by a cellophane membrane.

Since the reduction of nitrogen to ammonia in the above set ups is greater with dilute solution and since electrolysis of such dilute solutions gives rise to non-Faradaic electrolysis, there is probably something in common for the genesis of these two phenomena. Since hydrated electron formation near the cathode is one of the suggested explanations of non-Faradaic electrolysis⁵, it may be assumed that a steady state concentration of hydrated electrons builds up inside the cathode chamber. This is theoretically possible because electrons are being pumped in at the rate of about 10^{16} electrons/sec at about 1 mA whereas the hydrated electrons get annihilated at a rate constant of the order of 10^9 - 10^{11} /sec⁶. So the cathode chamber after sometimes becomes a veritable storehouse of electrons and this almost instantaneous build-up of electrons is responsible for the observed reduction of dissolved nitrogen to ammonia. This mechanism has also been considered to be responsible for the current increasing effect of cellophane membranes⁷.

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Utilisation of Indian Turpentine : Catalysed Conversion of Δ^8 -Carene to *p*- and *m*-Cymene over Platinum-Alumina

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INDIAN turpentine has not been exploited to the fullest extent. A major difficulty in its utilization is the presence of 3-carene to the extent of about 60%, which gets easily oxidised in air with resin formation¹. Consequently, the oil cannot be stored